

Assessing of Antibiotic Resistance in the Phage-Plasmids of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and Its Inhibitory Compound

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Abstract

Objectives: Antibiotic resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* pose an increasing risk for human health worldwide. A continuous monitoring the distribution of virulence and resistance-associated genes is required for early detection of successful *K. pneumoniae* lineages. In this study, whole genome sequences data was used to characterize phage-plasmids of *K. pneumoniae* isolated from different countries and its inhibitory compound was investigated for phage-plasmids.

Methods: Whole genomes sequences of 15 genetically similar phage-plasmids of *K. pneumoniae* strains were selected according to BlastN analysis. Antibiotic resistance and virulence associated genes were screened by using ResFinder, PhageAI, PlasmidFinder, PHASTEST and PhageGE tools. Later on, whole genome sequences of phage-plasmids were analysed for a stable region in the genome by MAUVE analysis. The stable region encoding protein and its candidate inhibitor molecule was analysed to observe the interaction between protein and inhibitory compound by molecular docking studies.

Results: Various antibiotic resistance genes involving Aminoglycosides and Beta-lactams were detected in screened 7 of 15 phage-plasmids. All the plasmids had Salmonella SSU5 prophage. Phylogenetic analysis results showed the phage-plasmid belonging to India or China. MAUVE analysis indicated that the region encoding Replication protein A were common stable region. Molecular docking studies proved an interaction occurring within Replication protein A and a derivate of Fabimycin.

Conclusions: The analysis showed that Replication protein A could be a target site for new drug designing. Additionally, Fabimycin could be used to control both phage-plasmids and its host *K. pneumoniae*, which could affect the severity and incidence of *K. pneumoniae* infections. Further studies *in vitro* and clinical studies could confirm present findings and also enhance our knowledge on phage-plasmids and new treatments against *K. pneumoniae* infections.

Keywords; antibiotic resistance, BLASTN, Fabimycin, molecular docking, phage-plasmids, Replication protein A.

1. INTRODUCTION

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a commensal, Gram-negative bacillus, characterized by its encapsulated and non-motile enteric nature. *K. pneumoniae* can cause a wide range of healthcare-associated infections, including pneumonia, bacteremia, meningitis, wound or surgical site infections (Martin & Bachman, 2018). The most crucial point in the life cycle of *K. pneumoniae* is gaining access to the body, as this influences whether its behaviour will be commensal or pathogenic. *K. pneumoniae* accounts for 8% of all the nosocomial infection, wherein pneumonia is the major cause of cases. *K. pneumoniae* infection occurs only when the bacterium is able to evade and overcome the host's primary and secondary immune responses that is a highly possible scenario in hospital settings. The spread of *K. pneumoniae* infection primarily occurs through person-to-person contact. Although less common, transmission can also happen via open wounds, unattended cuts, bruises, or environmental contamination.

Various outbreaks of *K. pneumoniae* infections have been documented globally. It is estimated that nearly 12% of all hospital-acquired pneumonia cases worldwide are caused by this pathogen (Ashurst & Dawson, 2023; Nirwati et al., 2019). As reported by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), approximately 80% of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae infections are attributed to *K. pneumoniae* (Ashurst & Dawson, 2023).

The World Health Organization (WHO) has classified this bacterial pathogen as a critical threat due to its acquired resistance to current drugs such as methicillin, penicillin, oxacillin, cefoxitin, and carbapenems (WHO, 2024). Consequently, the presence of β -lactamase enzymes, combined with alterations in efflux pumps, has facilitated the clonal diversification of antibiotic-resistant strains in this bacterium (Martin & Bachman, 2018; Reyes et al., 2019). Therefore, the current situation underscores the urgent need for the development of potent and novel therapeutic compounds to combat such pathogenic infections.

Obtaining complete genetic information of living organisms is crucial for gaining a comprehensive understanding of them as biological systems. Several bioinformatics databases and tools are available for the functional and structural annotation of hypothetical proteins. Computational approaches were extensively employed for the following of antibiotic resistance (Nguyen et al., 2018; Akinola et al., 2024). Recent advancements in medical and pharmaceutical sciences have prominently utilized data derived from whole genome sequences (Lam et al., 2021; Pranavathiyani et al., 2024). Within this dataset, the analysis of phages, plasmids and antibiotic resistomes hold considerable promise for the life sciences, facilitating deeper insights into the defence mechanisms employed by pathogens. Prophages are considered pivotal factors contributing to bacterial virulence, genomic diversification, fitness, and they are prevalent across bacterial genomes (Fortier & Sekulovic, 2013). Additionally, antibiotic resistance remains a significant concern (Nang et al., 2024). Identifying and classifying genes responsible for antibiotic resistance can facilitate the development of novel antibiotic compounds.

In this study, the whole genome sequences of selected 15 phage-plasmids from *Klebsiella pneumoniae* subsp. *pneumoniae* strains were investigated for their antibiotic resistance profiles and screened for a stable region which can be targeted by an inhibitory compound.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Blast analysis and sequence selection

Klebsiella pneumoniae subsp. *pneumoniae* HS11286 plasmid pKPHS1 sequence (NCBI Acc. No: CP003223.1), which was belonging to Salmonella SSU5 phage, was subjected to BLASTN search at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>, accessed on 28 December 2024). From the blast results, whole genome sequences of 15 phage-plasmids were selected by their position in

phylogenetic tree and the sequences were downloaded from the National Center for Biotechnology Information database (NCBI, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) (Table 1). The sequences are given in Supplementary data 1.

Table 1. The 15 selected whole-genome sequences of phage-plasmids from *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were used for analyses. “-” represents unknown. The sequences are listed according to their position in phylogenetic tree of blast analysis in Fig.1.

No	NCBI Accession Number	Country of Origin	Isolation Source	Bp Length	Collection/Submission Date
1	CP129187.1	China: Jiangsu	-	135702	Nov-2022/28-Jun-2023
2	CP152770.1	Norway	Blood: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	110383	2017/22-Mar-2024
3	CP166442.1	USA	Rectal Swab: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	106731	21-Apr-2024/15-May-2024
4	CP133013.1	India: Bangalore	Urine: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	122792	17-Mar-2023/11-Aug-2023
5	CP146193.1	China: Kunming	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	112792	11-Jan-2020/08-Feb-2024
6	CP138518.1	China: Wuhan	Urine: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	111727	26-Sep-2020/22-Sep-2023
7	CP107386.1	China: Wuhan	Sputum: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	111727	04-Dec-2018/07-Oct-2022
8	CP133391.1	India: Bangalore	Urine: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	122824	24-Feb-2023/24-Aug-2023
9	CP166074.1	Indonesia: Mataram	Lab stock	122802	11-Jul-2024/05-Aug-2024
10	MZ475705.1	China	Transconjugant	246861	15-Dec-2020/10-Jun-2021
11	CP107348.1	China: Wuhan	Sputum: <i>Homo sapiens</i>	111727	04-Dec-2018/07-Oct-2022
12	CP102393.1	China: Beijing	Blood	113637	19-Dec-2021/04-Aug-2022
13	OU877720.1	Spain	-	118859	19-Oct-2021
14	CP021962.1	USA	-	132217	13-Jun-2017
15	CP003223.1	China: Shanghai	-	122799	22-Dec-2011

2.2. Antibiotic resistome analysis

The antibiotic regions of the plasmids were determined by the bioinformatic method of Zankari et al. (2012). Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes were identified using the ResFinder 4.6.0 tool (<http://genepi.food.dtu.dk/resfinder>) with an identity threshold of 90%. Also, phage type and GC content was determined by PhageAI (<https://app.phage.ai/phages>) and plasmid replicons were determined with PlasmidFinder 2.1 (Carattoli et al., 2014) (<https://cge.food.dtu.dk/services/PlasmidFinder/>, accessed on 29 Dec 2024).

Sequences were analysed by accession numbers, using PHASTEST webserver (Wishart et al., 2023). PHASTEST results categorized phage genomes as intact, questionable, or incomplete based on the count of coding DNA sequences (CDS) linked to prophages and the detection of phage-associated genes. The phylogenetic tree of plasmid-phages was constructed by PhageGE (https://jason-zhao.shinyapps.io/PhageGE_Update) (Zhao et al., 2024).

2.3. Sequence alignment, Homology modelling, Protein prediction and Docking analysis

Progressive-MAUVE from the Geneious software (Geneious Prime® 2025.0.3) was used for determining the common regions among all genomes (Darling et al., 2010, Baysal et al., 2021a; Silme, 2024a). The unvarying genomic region was removed and the sequence was transformed into a protein sequence utilizing the ExPASy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate/>) (Gasteiger et al., 2003) and then loaded to the I-TASSER (Iterative Threading ASSEMBLY Refinement) server of Michigan University, US (<https://zhanglab.ccmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER>) for protein prediction (Yang et al., 2015; Baysal et al., 2021a). The homology models for the target protein, predicted by the ITASSER server system, were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (www.rcsb.org) (Table 2). Protein sequences were aligned, and homology modelling was conducted using the ExPASy proteomics server to obtain more structural information (Schwede et al., 2003).

Homology modelling and protein prediction analysis have directed to test the gene responsible for Replication Protein A, with a Fabimycin derivate as the ligand. The structure of Fabimycin derivate was retrieved from the PubChem database

(<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). This structure was used for docking calculations. The selected 3D structure of the ligand was retrieved from the PubChem Compound database in SDF format followed by conversion to mmol2 format. Cavity-detection guided blind docking is done primarily to analyse the interaction among Replication protein A and Fabimycin derivate (<http://clab.labshare.cn/cb-dock/>) (Liu et al., 2020). The docking results visualised by UCSF Chimera (ver. 1.18) and Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer (ver. 24.1.0.23298) (Pettersen et al., 2004; Biovia 2019). Later on, specific docking was done according to previous blind docking results and coordinates. The ligand parameters were analysed using the PRODRG online server (<http://prodr2.dyndns.org/cgi-bin/prodr2.cgi>) (Schüttelkopf & van Aalten, 2004). The shape complementarity principle was applied with clustering RMSD 4.0 for docking calculations. The flexible docking study was conducted using AutoDock v 4.0 (Trott & Olson, 2010). The interaction analysis of protein-ligand complexes and their amino acid positions with bond distances were calculated and visualized using PyMol software (ver. 3.1) (Schrödinger, 2024). Molecular docking simulation results were also confirmed again by the protein dock server SWISSDOCK (<http://www.swissdock.ch/docking>) within protein receptors and ligand interactions (Grosdidier, 2011). Later, Pymol was used to gain insight into their all-binding preferences within the active site of these receptors (Schrödinger, 2024).

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

3.1. Blast analysis

Blast analysis showed that many *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains have the Salmonella SSU5 phage sequences as chromosomal integrated prophage or phage-plasmid. 15 phage-plasmids were selected according to their positions in the phylogenetic tree of Blast analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Blast analysis of plasmid pKPHS1 sequence. The selected phage-plasmids utilized in further analyses are numbered.

3.2. Antibiotic resistome and sequence alignment analysis

Various antibiotic resistance genes were found 7 of 15 selected plasmids (Table 2). The predicted phenotypic results indicate there is resistance to unknown aminoglycoside, gentamicin, tobramycin, hygromycin, streptomycin, spectinomycin, amikacin, amoxicillin, amoxicillin+clavulanic acid, ampicillin, ampicillin+clavulanic acid, cefepime, cefixime, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, piperacillin, ertapenem, imipenem, meropenem, piperacillin+tazobactam, aztreonam, temocillin, ticarcillin, ceftazidime+avibactam, ceftriaxone, cephalothin, sulfamethoxazole, and fosfomycin chloramphenicol (Table 2). The 10th phage plasmid from Chinese origin was found to have the most antibiotic resistance regions, and it has higher nucleotide number than the others. It was also described as “*transconjugant*” in the NCBI system (in Table 1 & 2).

The distribution of phage-plasmids shows that there is particularly resistance to aminoglycoside and beta-lactam antibiotics (Table 1 & 2). These results and the genetic rearrangements obtained with Mauve analysis (Fig 2) indicated that the plasmid-phage is evolving to a wide range resistance to modern antibiotics in different regions of the world. Especially, the presence of phage-plasmids carrying antibiotic resistance genes in China and India, is consistent with research on the emerging antibiotic resistance in these two countries (Kumar et al., 2013; Qu et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2023; Nogrady, 2023; Iqbal, 2024). It has

been mentioned in previous studies that there is intensive antibiotic usage in food, animal husbandry and pharmacy in these countries (Taneja & Sharma, 2019; Wu, 2019), and it can be concluded this could be the main reason for bacteria evolving rapidly due to the antimicrobial pressure. The fact that most of these WGS data belongs to the last 4 years (Table 1) and the half of 15 randomly selected plasmids are carrying antibiotic resistance genes (Table 2) and the host bacteria could be attributed as hypervirulent.

Interestingly, phage.AI analysis classified 6 of the phage-plasmids as virulent and the left ones were temperate (Table 2). This property could affect the severity of pneumonia infection on patients. All plasmid replicons belong to IncFIB group (Table 2), which confirms previous studies that indicated extended spectrum β -lactamases are usually associated with IncF-type plasmids (Mahrault et al., 2019; Rocha-Gracia et al., 2022). Notably, IncF plasmids use postsegregational killing and addiction systems to ensure their propagation and maintenance among high-risk bacterial populations (Mathers et al., 2015).

Table 2. List of antibiotic resistance genes in the selected phage-plasmids.

Phage Properties				Resistance genes				
Plasmid ID	GC content (%)	Phage Types	Plasmid Replicons	Aminoglycoside	Beta-lactam	Sulfonamide	amphenicol	fosfomycin
1	50.41	Temperate	IncFIB	<i>aac(3)-IV</i> <i>aadA1</i> <i>aph(4)-Ia</i> <i>aadA1</i>	-	<i>sul3</i>	<i>cmlA1</i>	-
2	49.09	Temperate	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
3	49.19	Virulent	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
4	49.45	Temperate	IncFIB	-	<i>blaCTX-M-15</i>	-	-	-
5	48.98	Virulent	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
6	48.95	Virulent	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
7	48.95	Virulent	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
8	49.44	Temperate	IncFIB	-	<i>blaCTX-M-193</i>	-	-	-
9	49.47	Temperate	IncFIB	-	<i>blaCTX-M-14</i>	-	-	-
10	47.42	Temperate	IncFIB	<i>aac(6)-Ib3</i> <i>aadA1</i> <i>aph(3)-XV</i>	<i>blaCTX-M-3</i> <i>blaVIM-1</i> <i>blaTEM-1B</i>	-	<i>catB2</i>	<i>fosA3</i>
11	48.95	Virulent	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
12	49.11	Virulent	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
13	49.30	Temperate	IncFIB	-	-	-	-	-
14	49.12	Temperate	IncFIB	<i>aph(3)-VI</i>	<i>blaNDM-1</i>	-	-	-
15	49.46	Temperate	IncFIB	-	<i>blaCTX-M-14</i>	-	-	-

Figure 2. Progressive MAUVE analysis results of phage-plasmids. The region from left (purple), marked with red arrow, and lengthen 0-300 bp, shown to be genetically stable among all sequences.

The Mauve analysis revealed a genomic comparison among 15 different phage-plasmids, highlighting the presence of common regions in genome (Figure 2). The output from the genome comparison analysis exhibited variation and similarity based on the origins of the subtypes (Figure 2). Similar clustering patterns were observed among the same geographical regions. Subtypes with the same origin were grouped within the same sub-cluster, such as sequences 11 and 7 from China, Wuhan; 4 and 8 from India, Bangalore and 6 and 5 from Wuhan and Kunming in China. These findings indicate that plasmids especially from China and India exhibit similar genetic diversity as geographically they are neighbours. Additionally, the phylogenetic tree constructed by PhageGE demonstrated the presence of 3 main groups (A, B, C) in Figure 3, further validating the Mauve results. The recent phylogenetic data indicates the

beginning of phage-plasmids evolution process is either China or India, which should be confirmed with further studies.

Figure 3. The phylogenetic tree of within selected 15 phage-plasmids show 3 main branches; A, B, C.

The phylogenetic tree corresponded to the Mauve map and provides information about the spread of the phage-plasmids in countries. China or India was the emerging point and it spreads to other countries from these origins. It can be predicted that the increase in transportation and trade, especially between close and far countries, is a result of this dissemination. It is not possible to claim anything of limited 15 sequences which is not representing the pathogen profile of the country but the possibility of an epidemic is a well-known fact, and in this respect, the phage-plasmid distribution in other countries should be examined with expanded further studies. It is known that these phage plasmids affect the bacterial infection and antibiotic resistance. Therefore, it should also be investigated that the *Salmonella*-derived phage hosted by *K. pneumoniae* can increase the incidence of disease development.

As described in previous studies, phages are foreign and immunogenic particles capable of eliciting humoral immune responses and triggering the production of antiphage antibodies (Sulakvelidze & Barrow, 2005; Majewska et al., 2015; Silme 2024a; 2024b). Additionally, Sweere et al. (2019) reported that a bacteriophage linked to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Pa) triggers antiviral defence mechanisms in humans and hinders the elimination of bacterial infections. These results indicate that the engagement between immune cells and phage-infected Pa led to the synthesis of phage RNA, suggesting that a natural, unaltered bacteriophage may have the capability to produce mRNA within human cells.

The circular gene distribution of the phage-plasmid 1 (China: Jiangsu) according to PHASTEST results is shown in Figure 4. Gene distributions of all phage-plasmids are given in Supplementary data S2. In Table 3, it was determined that 15 plasmids contained the Salmonella phage SSU5 (NCBI Acc. No: NC_018843) and 14 of these contained intact phage. Region lengths and GC contents varied among all phages. A recent study has shown that a plasmid in *K. pneumoniae* strain Kp1604 was predicted to be an intact Salmonella phage SSU5 and the phage could contribute to the host defence against the transported DNA elements (Cai et al., 2022). Further studies on this mechanism could help us understand, how it provides adaptive phenotypes to host during infection.

Table 3. List of phage properties according to PHASTEST results.

Plasmid ID	Region	Region Length (Kb)	Completeness	#Total Proteins	Region Position	Most Common Phage	GC content (%)
1	1	52.3	questionable	43	1550-53924	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	52.26
	2	56.3	intact	56	46860-103245	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	51.31
2	1	92.3	intact	90	17908-110253	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.21
3	1	77.2	intact	78	1550-78766	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.32
4	1	64.1	intact	70	26523-90658	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	50.31
5	1	89.3	intact	80	1550-90868	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	48.85
6	1	92.6	intact	83	1-92641	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	48.75
7	1	80.4	intact	77	1-80454	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.20
	2	20.9	questionable	32	90403-111370	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.76
8	1	64.1	intact	70	26524-90687	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	50.31
9	1	64.1	intact	68	26524-90665	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	50.37
10	1	51.1	Incomplete	50	89918-141106	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.42
	2	39.5	questionable	33	141031-180549	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.43
11	1	80.4	Intact	77	1-80454	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.20
	2	20.9	questionable	32	90403-111370	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.76
12	1	90.1	intact	82	1550-91713	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.01
13	1	29.7	Incomplete	28	1-29774	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.22
	2	59	intact	66	27379-86402	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	50.00
14	1	63.6	intact	63	35850-99511	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	49.07
	2	64.1	intact	74	26524-90662	PHAGE_Salmon_SSU5_NC_018843	50.36

Figure 4. Example plasmid 1 (China: Jiangsu) to show circular genomic distribution of genes. Detailed information on plasmid genes is given in Supplementary data S2.

3.3. Sequence alignment, Homology modelling, Protein prediction and Docking analysis

In the Mauve analysis, it was observed that the initial 0-320 bp region was the unvarying region (Figure 2, 5). Swiss dock analysis of this region showed us that it is Replication protein A (gene: A0A0H3GVC2_KLEPH, organism: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* subsp *pneumoniae* (strain HS11286), <https://www.uniprot.org/uniprotkb/A0A0H3GVC2/entry>). This protein can be used as a target site for the development of antiphage-plasmid molecules. Although the I-TASSER results were predicted the highest PDBs and were listed in Table 4, the predicted proteins were mostly various bacterial replication initiation proteins. The docking simulations was done considering Swiss dock results (Supplementary data S3).

I-TASSER analysis of this region reveals that the ligand is a nucleoside (acid) drug called (2E)-3-[(7S)-7-amino-8-oxo-6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-5H-pyrido[2,3-b]azepin-3-yl]-N-methyl-N-[(3-methyl-1-benzofuran-2-yl)methyl]prop-2-enamide (National Center for Biotechnology Information, 2025) which is a derivative of Fabimycin (Supplementary data S3). A patent on this nucleoside (acid) drug has been found and there is also a related clinical trial within (Hergenrother et al., 2021; Chia Tai Tianqing Co., Ltd., 2024).

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MLSAVNDMLSAVRYMLPTVLCMLSAVIDVCCQRLEPKGIHMSTKNKKESEIKEIPEDNEI  
LEEDALNLYTGDLVPNSNNTVQPIALMRLGLFVPTLKGTKNSSRNKSNMIDASRELVQLE  
VARSEGYSNIKITGPRLDMDHDFKTWVG VVRSLAEYGEPTGRVELSITKFAKFCGYSSQ  
IRKTLRDRLTNSLLK
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Figure 5. The submitted sequence results were transformed into an amino acid sequence through the ExPASy proteomics server (<https://web.expasy.org/translate>) to facilitate structural analysis utilizing the I-TASSER server.

Table 4. Homology modelling of the proteins using I-TASSER (<https://zhanglab.cmb.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER>) considering the specific sequence. *The highest PDB hit was 2nra.

Rank	PDB Hit	Identity 1	Identity 2	Coverage	Norm. Z-score
1*	2nra	0.07	0.22	0.90	1.69
2	6h24	0.08	0.17	0.26	1.19
3	5ubfA	0.19	0.15	0.44	1.08
4	2nra	0.06	0.22	0.35	1.06
5	6h24	0.12	0.17	0.35	1.08
6	2z9o	0.14	0.19	0.43	1.06
7	2z9o	0.17	0.19	0.74	1.08
8	5ubf	0.21	0.18	0.43	1.03
9	6klcA	0.21	0.17	0.85	0.60
10	7tb0A	0.12	0.16	0.85	0.68

Blind docking analysis of Replication protein A with the Fabimycin derivative showed there is an interaction between them (Supplementary data S4). This interaction was confirmed with AutoDock (Fig 6) and the binding energy was -7.82 kcal/J (Supplementary data S3). These results indicate Fabimycin derivative could both interrupt the replication machinery of phage-plasmid and the bacteria. A previous study also confirmed that Fabimycin was found to be a promising antibiotic candidate which is effective against more than 200 clinical isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*, including a challenging urinary tract infection model (Parker et al., 2022). This drug candidate focuses on

Targeting an invariant region in the genome could be critical point in purpose of drug designing. In accordance with the previous studies that the targeted region could be selected in the genome (Baysal et al., 2021a; 2021b; Baysal & Silme, 2021; Ghafoor et al., 2024; Silme, 2024a; 2024b). These results indicated that effective and low-labour cost drug finding could be possible on any targeted genomic region if the invariant sequences are available.

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a leading international problem. In 2019, the number of deaths worldwide linked to antimicrobial resistance reached 1.27 million. In that year, AMR could have led to 5 million fatalities, with one in five of those who died from AMR being children under the age of five (Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators, 2022). In 2015, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control estimated that the EU and European Economic Area experienced 671,689 infections linked to antibiotic-resistant bacteria, leading to 33,110 fatalities. The majority were acquired in medical environments (Cassini et al., 2019). Development of new methods for challenging AMR is a primary goal in sustainable healthcare systems (Aslam et al., 2024).

Recent studies indicate that phage-plasmids are prevalent and transfer a wide variety of clinically significant antibiotic resistance genes across bacteria (Pfeifer et al., 2021; 2022; Cai et al., 2022). Despite their ecological significance, most of these elements have not been characterized and their evolution as phage-plasmids remain poorly understood. Further multi-disciplinary studies with the collaboration of medicine, pharmacology and bioinformatics are necessary for continuous monitoring AMR and developing new treatments *in silico* and *in vitro*.

Although this study evaluated a small number of phage-plasmids, the data provided contribute to the understanding of the molecular epidemiology of resistance-mediating phage-plasmids across various countries. In recent years, cheap and fast WGS techniques was successfully applied to characterize antibiotic resistance among *K. pneumoniae* strains. A comprehensive *K. pneumoniae* database of genomes in each country is necessary for a complete understanding of the genome plasticity of these organisms and can significantly improve the tracking of antibiotic resistance among strains.

4. CONCLUSION

This study of *K. pneumoniae* phage-plasmids identified a wide range of antibiotic resistance genes to clinically important antibiotics. Phylogenetic studies show distribution of these phage-plasmids belong to India or China. These phage-plasmids could affect the severity and incidence of *K. pneumoniae* infections. Mauve analysis indicated that the region coding Replication protein A is genetically stable with low variations and could be a target point for new drug designs. Additionally, molecular docking studies indicated a derivate of Fabimycin targeting Replication protein A could be used against both phage-plasmids and its host *K. pneumoniae*. Further studies *in vitro* and clinical trials could confirm these findings and also widen our knowledge on phage-plasmids and new treatments against *K. pneumoniae* infections.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

RSS: conceptualization, resources, funding acquisition, project administration, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing.

ETHICS COMMITTEE APPROVAL: This study utilized whole genome sequences available from NCBI. Ethical approval was deemed unnecessary as the research did not involve human or animal subjects, nor did it entail primary cell cultures derived from human or animal subjects.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: The author has no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT: All relevant data are provided in the paper and supplementary data files. The bacterial genome sequences downloaded from NCBI can be accessed via the accession numbers given in the article.

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